

FACESHEET EFFECTS ON THE LOW VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGES IN TITANIUM/GFRP HYBRID LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Hybrid materials comprised of thin layers of metal alloy and fibre-reinforced polymer have excellent fatigue resistance and damage tolerance, and they are categorized as Fibre-Metal Laminates (FMLs). To date, aluminum alloy based FMLs such as ARALL (Al/aramid fibre) and GLARE (Al/grass fibre) have been applied to several military and commercial aircraft [1]. In recent years, investigations of titanium alloy/CFRP laminates (a.k.a. TiGr laminates) as FMLs have increased, and these laminates are thought to be promising materials that withstand the severe environment of advanced supersonic aircrafts that require operating temperatures as high as 177°C (350°F).

Many studies on the detailed characterization of impact damage of aluminum-based FMLs have been conducted by Vlot *et al.* [2] and other researchers. As for TiGr laminates, Cortés *et al.* [3] revealed energy-absorbing mechanisms during impact. Bernhardt *et al.* [4] characterized the impact response of TiGr by two modes that differed by failure or non-failure of the bottom titanium ply. A few studies have numerically calculated of the impact responses of FMLs [5, 6]. In these studies, however, the extent and overall size of the internal damages in the in-plane direction were not evaluated sufficiently, since the damages were examined using cross-sectional images because titanium alloy layers as facesheets make it difficult to observe internal damages via X-radiography.

In this regard, authors have investigated impact damages in Ti/GFRP laminates as titanium alloy based FML systems, and developed a FE model that represent impact responses and damage behavior in the laminates. This previous report concluded that interlaminar delamination in GFRP layer expanded sharply due to fracture in the titanium layer on the side opposite the impact with more than certain

threshold impact energy [7]. With a sandwich structure of metal facesheets and the FRP core, the metal layers shield the FRP core from impact damage caused by out-of-plane impact loading. However, the effects of metal layers at each position on internal damages in the laminates have yet to be elucidated fully so far.

The present paper reports on low-velocity impact tests on Ti/GFRP laminates as with the previous report. Impact-induced damages in the laminates are observed in detail, and their overall size in the in-plane direction is focused on. The role of the outer titanium ply is also evaluated by relating observed internal damages and fracture of the titanium layer. Furthermore, impact responses and damage behaviour of/in the Ti/GFRP laminates are obtained by dynamic FE analyses in order to confirm the experimental results.

2 Experimental

Ti/GFRP laminates examined in this study were manufactured by bonding titanium alloy sheets (Ti-6Al-4V, 140µm) to cross-plyed GFRP laminates (GF/epoxy prepreg: CW tapes, Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd.), with epoxy adhesive (DP-460, Sumitomo 3M, Ltd.). Prior to manufacturing, the titanium sheets and the GFRP laminates were sanded with abrasive paper in order to improve adhesion. Table 1 lists the mechanical properties of these constituent materials obtained by static tensile tests (0.5mm/min. RT). Specimens subjected to the impact loading were laminates comprised of two outer layers of titanium sheets sandwiching a GFRP layer as core material, [Ti/0₃/90₃]_S (Ti/GFRP laminates), and that with a single titanium layer [Ti/0₃/90₃/90₃/0₃]. Two impact tests were conducted on the Ti/GFRP laminates with a single titanium layer. In one test, the laminates were impacted from the titanium facesheet (test series Titanium facesheet IMPacted

(TIMP)); in the other, they were impacted from the GFRP layer side (test series GFRP layer side IMPacted (GIMP)). The average thickness and the aerial weight of the Ti/GFRP laminates and TIMP/GIMP were 1.89mm and 2.56g/cm², and 1.55mm and 2.01g/cm², respectively.

The square specimens (100×100 mm²) were clamped by two steel panels with an 80mm diameter central opening and fixed with epoxy adhesive (Araldite, Huntsman); these units were mounted in the testing machine. Low-velocity impact tests were conducted using a drop-weight test frame with a pneumatic rebound brake system. A steel impactor with a 10mm diameter hemispherical head was used, and the impactor mass was 2kg for all tests. Impact velocity and impact energy were calculated from the drop height of the impactor.

3 Experimental Results and Discussions

3.1 Observation of Impact Damages, and Impact Responses

Figure 1 re-presents photographs of damage of Ti/GFRP laminates obtained by previous study [7] at impact energy normalized by the aerial weights of 1.84Jcm²/g and 1.91Jcm²/g. Figure 2 presents photographs of impact damages in the test series TIMP and GIMP with an impact energy of 1.46Jcm²/g and 1.95Jcm²/g. The titanium layer on the side opposite the impact was removed in order to observe internal damages in the GFRP layer with the naked eye. Overall, no major differences in damage modes were observed between layers of TIMP and GIMP, and Ti/GFRP laminates. The damage modes of TIMP remained unchanged, regardless of the increase of impact energy. In contrast, a single crack was initiated in the titanium layer (on the non-impacted side) in GIMP with an impact energy of 1.95Jcm²/g, and extensive growth of the interlaminar delamination in the GFRP layer was obtained due to the occurrence of this crack. This damage behaviour in GIMP (i.e., interaction between the single crack in the titanium layer and interlaminar delamination in the GFRP layer) was equivalent to that obtained using Ti/GFRP laminates with two outer layers of titanium. It is noteworthy that damage states of the GFRP layer indicated one severe bending crack that passed through the impact centre for TIMP. In contrast, several small cracks, so to say splitting in the 0° ply, were presented for GIMP. It should be noted that this difference in damage in the GFRP layer was also obtained when a single crack occurred in the titanium layer for GIMP, and then

the interlaminar delamination widened with higher impact energy.

Figure 3 plots the interlaminar delaminated area in the GFRP core in Ti/GFRP laminates, and test series TIMP and GIMP as a function of normalized impact energy. This figure also includes the delamination area in cross-plyed GFRP laminates with no titanium layer [0₄/90₄]_S for comparison. The delaminated area in cross-plyed GFRP laminates increased continuously with impact energy, and TIMP followed this behaviour in almost the same delaminated area. Hence, the titanium layer on the impacted side was assumed to have little effect on interlaminar delamination in the GFRP layer. GIMP suppressed the spreading of delamination, compared to the cross-plyed GFRP laminates and TIMP with an impact energy of less than 1.5Jcm²/g. Since the titanium layer on the non-impacted side was loaded in tension and plastically deformed without other damages such as cracks, the reinforcement achieved by the stiffness of this titanium layer effectively prevented internal damages of the laminates. However, when a single crack occurred in the titanium layer on the non-impacted side with normalized impact energy greater than 1.5Jcm²/g, similar to the behaviour of Ti/GFRP laminates, the delaminated area in the GFRP layer increased to almost the same value as that in the cross-plyed GFRP laminates and TIMP. Therefore, above this impact energy level, the effect of the titanium layer to prevent the growth of interlaminar delamination in the GFRP layer was regarded to be no longer available. It should be noted that the energy level at which the “jump” of the delaminated area in GIMP was exhibited declined compared to that of the Ti/GFRP laminates because test series GIMP, which did not have a titanium layer at the top, was less rigid. These results indicate that a titanium layer on the non-impacted side with no impact-induced cracks effectively prevent the spread of interlaminar delamination in the GFRP layer.

The load-time traces of Ti/GFRP laminates during impact events are shown in Fig. 4. Except for low noise, a smooth curve was obtained at 1.84Jcm²/g. An extensive decrease and fluctuation of the load were exhibited after 2.6msec at 1.91Jcm²/g. This corresponds to the occurrence of a single crack in the titanium layer on the non-impacted side, which decreased the local bending stiffness near the impact point. For the impact responses of test series TIMP and GIMP, similar trend compared to the Ti/GFRP laminates was obtained for GIMP. Again, the impact

responses were dominated by crack initiation in the titanium layer on the non-impacted side.

Thus far, the roles of outer titanium facesheets on each side in preventing internal damages of the laminates have yet to be clarified, except that the titanium layer on the non-impacted side suppressed interlaminar delamination and severe matrix cracking in the GFRP layer as seen in Fig. 2. Therefore, impact damages in the GFRP layers of test series TIMP and GIMP at $3.90\text{Jcm}^2/\text{g}$ were observed using the cross-sectional views in Fig. 5. Compared to the damages in GIMP, the 90° ply of the GFRP layer in TIMP beneath the impact point crushed with a number of matrix cracks pushing the lower 0° ply outward and interlaminar delamination between the 90° and the lower 0° plies remained wide-open. These results indicate that the out-of-plane deformation of TIMP remained larger after impact loading than that of GIMP. This difference can be attributed to the energy absorption of the titanium layer on the non-impacted side, where larger plastic deformation and a fracture in tension were exhibited. Four-point bending tests using the GFRP layer after impact loading were conducted in order to provide a detailed description of the function of the titanium facesheets by evaluating the difference between damaged conditions of the GFRP layers of TIMP and those of GIMP.

3.2 Four-point Bending Tests after the Impact Loading

GFRP layers taken from test series TIMP or GIMP after impact loading with an impact energy of $1.95\text{Jcm}^2/\text{g}$ were used for the specimens. These specimens had almost the same interlaminar delaminated area at the given impact energy (see Fig. 3). For four-point bending tests, specimens were set on the jig so that the non-impacted side would be loaded in compression by bending. With this setup, buckling failure in the convex portion on the side opposite the impact was the dominant damage mode. Therefore, the residual out-of-plane deformation of each laminate after impact loading could be evaluated quantitatively.

Figure 6 presents the results of four-point bending tests. Although large standard deviations were exhibited, the GFRP core taken from GIMP had both higher residual bending strength and bending stiffness than that taken from TIMP. These differences can be attributed to more severe matrix cracks and larger residual out-of-plane deformation presented to the GFRP layer in TIMP by impact loading, as mentioned above. This damage made it

easier for the GFRP layer of TIMP to buckle due to its low ability to withstand the bending load.

4 Finite Element Analysis of Impact Loading on Ti/GFRP Laminates

4.1 Development of Numerical Models

To clarify the relationship between the internal and external damages as well as the effect of titanium facesheets, dynamic explicit analysis was carried out using the finite element code ABAQUS (Simulia, Dassault Systèmes). From the symmetric properties of each damage mode, one-half of the laminates were modeled in three dimensions as shown in Fig. 7. The impactor and each layer in the laminates were modeled as separate parts. Interface layers were inserted into each of two $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces in the GFRP layer to represent interlaminar delamination. For TIMP and GIMP, titanium and adhesive layers on the non-impact side or the impact side were removed, respectively. Element types for each part are tabulated in Table 2.

Isotropic elasticity and metal plasticity were applied to the titanium and adhesive layers. Johnson-Cook strain-rate-dependent yield stress was also applied to the titanium layers. Orthotropic elasticity in the plane stress field was used for each of the GFRP plies. Material properties were based on the experimental values (Table 1).

The Hashin failure criteria [8] implemented in ABAQUS was applied to each ply in the GFRP layer to represent the damage initiation caused by impact loading. Table 3 indicates the strength of unidirectional GFRP plates required by Hashin failure criteria. The behaviour of cohesive elements used in the interface layers was defined directly in terms of a traction-separation law, and damage was assumed to be initiated when the following quadratic nominal stress criterion [9] was satisfied.

$$\left\{ \frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_s}{t_s^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_t}{t_t^0} \right\}^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

Here, t_n denotes the normal shear traction; t_s and t_t denote two shear tractions; and t_n^0 , t_s^0 and t_t^0 are their peak values. The symbol $\langle \rangle$ denotes the Macaulay bracket. The parameters used for the criteria are presented in Table 4. With these criteria satisfied, damage growth in each damage mode was simulated by stiffness degradation using fracture energy. Sizes of the interfacial debonding and the single crack in the titanium layer on the non-impact side were measured directly from the specimens after impact loading. The debonding was assumed to

be circular in the analysis. These damages were manually applied during analysis by releasing the tie constraint in the appropriate part at moments based on the experimental load-time curves. The impact loads were represented by applying the initial velocity calculated from the drop height to the impactor.

4.2 Numerical Results of Impact Behaviour of Ti/GFRP Laminates

Calculated load-time responses with impact energy of 1.84 and 1.91Jcm²/g were compared to the experimental results in Fig. 8. With 1.84Jcm²/g, the loads indicated a smooth curve because no crack occurred in the titanium layer. On the other hand, initiation of a single crack in the titanium layer on the non-impacted side at 1.91Jcm²/g resulted in a decrease and fluctuation of the load response. Though the fluctuation in the second part of the curve observed in the experiment was spiky compared to that obtained in the analysis, it is assumed that load response was qualitatively represented.

Figure 9 plots the experiment-derived and calculated interlaminar delaminated areas in the lower 0°/90° interface of the Ti/GFRP laminates. Compared with the predicted delamination with no cracking, the “jump” of delaminated area near an impact energy of 1.88Jcm²/g was predicted well by the analyses as well as the experimental results. These results confirmed that the sharp increase of delamination area in the GFRP layer was induced by crack initiation in the titanium layer on the side opposite the impact, as indicated in the experiments.

Next, the calculated damage in the lower 0° ply of the GFRP layer in test series TIMP and GIMP was observed. Damage variables in the matrix tensile mode near the impact point are presented in Fig. 10. With an impact energy of 1.46Jcm²/g, damage was localized along the 0° direction like the bending crack in TIMP. In GIMP, however, a matrix tensile fracture spread in the 90° direction and formed several small lines like splitting. With 1.95Jcm²/g, though a single crack appeared in the titanium layer on the non-impacted side, low-level damage as splitting dispersed into a wide region. These results obviously agreed well with the experimental results shown in Fig. 2. Figure 11 shows displacement traces of a node in the lower 0° ply under the impact point. When the average value of the vibrating portion was taken as the residual out-of-plane deformation of the plate, the lower 0° ply in TIMP exhibited larger deformation with an impact energy of 1.95Jcm²/g. This result was assumed to contribute

to the difference in residual bending strength and bending stiffness obtained by the four-point bending tests. These calculated results support experimental evidence that the titanium layer on the side opposite the impact effectively prevents damages in the GFRP core of Ti/GFRP laminates.

5 Conclusions

The effect of a titanium layer on the low-velocity impact damages of the Ti/GFRP laminates has been evaluated in experimental and numerical ways based on the damage state of the GFRP core in Ti/GFRP laminates. The observed experimental results and four-point bending tests indicate that under low-velocity impact loading, the stiffening achieved by the titanium layer that undertake the tensile load on the side opposite the impact works effectively. Furthermore, even if a single crack is formed in the titanium layer on the non-impacted side, out-of-plane deformation and damage growth, except for interlaminar delamination, are suppressed because the impact energy is absorbed by the plastic deformation and occurrence of the crack in this titanium layer.

Numerical models that represent impact loading on Ti/GFRP hybrid laminates have been developed. The effects of titanium facesheets on impact responses and internal damages in the laminates have been identified through these analyses. Drop and fluctuation of loads in the impact responses due to crack initiation in the titanium layer on the non-impacted side were successfully obtained by dynamic analyses, and the behaviour of interlaminar delamination in the GFRP layer was comparable with that in the experiments. Also, calculated development of the internal damages in the epoxy matrix of the GFRP layer agreed well with the experimental results. Thus, the titanium layer on the side opposite the impact dominates the impact behaviour of Ti/GFRP laminates and plays a major role in preventing damages in the GFRP core.

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Table 1 Properties of constituent materials.

	t [mm]	density [kg/m ³]	E [GPa]	ν	σ_y [MPa]
Titanium	0.14	4500	85.9	0.380	826
Adhesive	0.20	2000	1.62	0.384	27.5

	t [mm]	density [kg/m ³]	E ₁₁ [GPa]	E ₂₂ [GPa]	ν_{12}	G ₁₂ [GPa]	G ₂₃ [GPa]
GFRP UD	0.101	2000	36.9	10.0	0.32	3.30	3.60

Fig.1 Impact damages in Ti/GFRP laminates [7].

Fig.3 Interlaminar delamination area in GFRP core.

Fig.4 Load-time traces of Ti/GFRP laminates.

Fig.5 Cross-sections of GFRP core in TIMP and GIMP.

Fig.2 Impact damages in test series TIMP and GIMP at impact energy of (a) 1.46 Jcm²/g and (b) 1.95 Jcm²/g.

Fig.6 Residual bending strength and bending stiffness of GFRP core after impact loading ($1.95 \text{ J cm}^2/\text{g}$) obtained by four-point bending tests.

Fig.7 Schematic of the FE model.

Table 2 Element type for each part.

Part name	Element type
Impactor	Rigid element: R3D4
Ti alloy layer	Solid element: C3D8R
Adhesive layer	
GFRP ply layer	Shell continuum element: SC8R
Interface layer	Cohesive element: COH3D8

Table 3 Strength and fracture energy of unidirectional GFRP plates used for Hashin failure criteria.

Strength [MPa] / Fracture energy [N/mm]	0° direction	90° direction
Tensile mode	820 / 32.0	80.6 / 4.5
Compressive mode	500 / 20.0	322 / 4.5
Longitudinal shear mode	54.5 / ---	
Transverse shear mode	161.2 / ---	

Table 4 Parameters for cohesive element.

	Normal mode	1 direction	2 direction
Nominal stress [MPa]	65.0	57.5	57.5
Fracture energy [N/mm]	5.0	0.5	0.5

Fig.8 Numerical results of load-time traces of the Ti/GFRP laminates.

Fig.9 Numerical results of delaminated area in the GFRP core as a function of normalized impact energy.

Fig.10 Damage variables (matrix tensile mode) in the lower 0° ply of GFRP core obtained by FE analysis.

Fig.11 Displacement traces of the node of the lower 0° ply at the centre of the plate.